

LIPID COMPOSITION OF THE AERIAL PARTS OF SAGE (SALVIA SP.)**¹ Normakhamatov N.S.****¹ A.A. Turaboev****¹ Ch.T. Toshtemirova****² F.A. Kodiralieva****² A.A. Siddikova**¹ Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute, Tashkent, Uzbekistan² Institute of Plant Chemistry named after Academician S. Yu. Yunusov
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Relevance: Plants of the genus *Salvia* are rich in biologically active compounds. Studying the lipid complex of the above-ground parts of sage is important for assessing its potential as a source of functionally valuable polyunsaturated fatty acids and related components.

The aim of the study: To study the quantitative and qualitative composition of lipids in the above-ground part of sage, to determine the ratio of neutral and polar lipids, their fatty acid profile and to identify biologically significant components.

Materials and methods: Object – air-dried above-ground part of sage (*Salvia sp.*).

Neutral lipids (NL) were extracted with gasoline (b.p. 75–80°C), and polar lipids (PL) were extracted using the Folch method with a chloroform–methanol mixture (2:1). The resulting fractions were purified to remove impurities and analyzed spectrophotometrically and by thin-layer chromatography. Fatty acid composition was determined by gas chromatography.

Results: The moisture content of the raw material was 7.1%. Total lipids were 9.2% of the above-ground part weight, including 7.8% of NL and 1.4% of PL.

Chlorophyll pigments were detected in the NL: 11.7 mg/l chlorophyll a and 5.1 mg/l chlorophyll b.

The qualitative composition of NL is represented by hydrocarbons, fatty acid esters with phytosterols and triterpenols, triacylglycerides, free fatty acids and alcohols, triterpenols, phytosterols and chlorophyll pigments.

Glycolipids and phospholipids have been identified in the composition of PL.

The fatty acid profile includes 9 components:

– linoleic (44.3%) and oleic (19.9%) acids dominate in NL;

– linoleic (34.9%) and α -linolenic (29.3%) acids predominate in PL.

The total content of unsaturated fatty acids is 79.1% in NL and 77.2% in PL, saturated – 20.9% and 22.8%, respectively.

Conclusions. The aerial parts of sage contain significant amounts of lipids, including biologically valuable polyunsaturated fatty acids. The data obtained confirm its potential as a source of lipids with potential functional activity.